

Grant Agreement n° 101115488

Double-Active Membranes for a sustainable CO₂ cycle
01/11/2023 – 31/10/2026

EIC Pathfinder Challenge: Carbon dioxide and Nitrogen management and valorisation

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Dissemination, website, project logo, visual identity

Abstract:

This deliverable aims at presenting the logo of the DAM4CO₂ project, as well as the first version of the project website, and project profiles on the different social media.

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Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EIC	European Innovation Council
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
PIC	Participant Identification Code
COO	Coordinator
BEN	Beneficiary

Document History

Version	Date	Contributors	Description
v1.0	14/12/2023	Alessio Fuoco (CNR) Elisa Esposito (CNR)	Initial draft
v1.0	18/12/2023		Sent to EB
V2.0	29/12/2023	Alessio Fuoco (CNR) Elisa Esposito (CNR)	Final draft

Approval History

	Name Surname	Date of Approval
WP Leader	Elisa Esposito	18/12/2023
Coordinator*	Alessio Fuoco	29/12/2023

*on behalf of the EB

Introduction

This report constitutes the deliverable n° D8.1 of the project DAM4CO₂, and it is related to the launch of the project logo, the project website, and the social media profiles. Thus, D8.1 reports the logo that will be used as well as the first version of two of the most important dissemination channels throughout the project duration, i.e. the website and social media profiles.

The project logo

The project logo has been created by INSTM and it is reported in Figure 1. It ensures a distinctively visual identity of the project. The logo will be used to recall the project in all the communication and dissemination activities on any used platform (e.g., social media, website, poster and oral templates). This will allow to have a clear identity of DAM4CO₂ that will be easily identified.

Figure 1 DAM4CO₂ logo

The website

The project website is hosted on CNR servers and it is accessible using the following link: www.dam4co2.eu.

The current layout of the header of the website, that will be updated in the next few months, is the following:

Figure 2 Layout of the header of the DAM4CO₂ project

It reports all the tools to navigate between the different pages of the website that is currently composed by the following sections:

- Home
- About DAM4CO₂

- Consortium
- Publications
- News & Events
- EIC Portfolio
- Contact us
- Our Funding
- Members Area

The project website is crafted by CNR and this will allow the update of the project at least with monthly frequency and in case of major events, as well as any modification and improvement required for its optimal exploitation.

All the sections report public information about the DAM4CO₂ project, such as the partners with the links to their official webpages, scopes and objectives, events organized by the consortium (e.g. kick-off meeting) or where the results are presented. Moreover, the section EIC Portfolio reports all the projects related to the call: “EIC Pathfinder Challenge: Carbon dioxide and Nitrogen management and valorisation” and will be updated as soon as the portfolio website will be active.

All project partners can login to the “members Area” via this link www.dam4co2.eu/private_area/ or from the official site. This section allows the exchange of documents and data in private. Each WP has its own folder, but the structure can be rearranged depending on the needs of the consortium.

Figure 3 screenshot of the members area of the project website

The Social Media Profiles

Social Media profiles were created on X (ex-Twitter), Instagram and LinkedIn in order to engage different groups of stakeholders. The account name @dam4co2 has been used for all the accounts, and the logo is used as picture profile to maintain the visual identity of the project. It is foreseen to create also a YouTube profile in order to share webinars and videos prepared during the project. Below, the screenshots of the project profiles on the different social media are reported (Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6).

← **DAM4CO2**
5 post

DAM4CO2

@dam4co2 Ti segue

DAM4CO2 is a multidisciplinary EU project based on the process intensification of CO₂ capture & conversion by preparation of a Double Active Membrane

📅 Iscrizione: novembre 2023

97 following 23 follower

 Seguito da elena Tocci, Grazia Bezzu e altri 7 che segui

Figure 4 screenshot of the X (ex-twitter) profile of the project.

<https://twitter.com/dam4co2>

Figure 5 screenshot of the Instagram profile of the project.
<https://www.instagram.com/dam4co2/>

Figure 6 screenshot of the LinkedIn profile of the project.
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/dam4co2>

Consortium of DAM4CO₂

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT	999979500
2	BEN	INSTM	CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO NAZIONALE PER LA SCIENZA E TECNOLOGIA DEI MATERIALI	IT	999991237
3	BEN	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	999864846
4	BEN	PRIMALCHIT	PRIMALCHIT SOLUTIONS	ES	892236168
5	BEN	Me-Sep	ME-SEP SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA	PL	887256382
6	BEN	USwan	SWANSEA UNIVERSITY	UK	999862033
7	BEN	UEdin	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UK	999974941

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**UK Research
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